

Probing Anomalous $WW\gamma$ and WWZ Couplings with Polarized Electron Beam at the LHeC and FCC-Ep Collider

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Abstract—We study the anomalous $WW\gamma$ and WWZ couplings by calculating total cross sections of two processes at the LHeC with electron beam energy $E_e=140$ GeV and the proton beam energy $E_p=7$ TeV, and at the FCC-ep collider with the polarized electron beam energy $E_e=80$ GeV and the proton beam energy $E_p=50$ TeV. At the LHeC with electron beam polarization, we obtain the results for the difference of upper and lower bounds as (0.975, 0.118) and (0.285, 0.009) for the anomalous $(\Delta\kappa_\gamma, \lambda_\gamma)$ and $(\Delta\kappa_Z, \lambda_Z)$ couplings, respectively. As for FCC-ep collider, these bounds are obtained as (1.101, 0.065) and (0.320, 0.002) at an integrated luminosity of $L_{int}=100$ fb $^{-1}$.

Keywords—Anomalous Couplings, Future Circular Collider, Large Hadron electron Collider, W -boson and Z -boson.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE $SU(2)\times U(1)$ gauge symmetry of the Standard Model (SM) results in the triple gauge boson interactions. A precise determination of the trilinear gauge boson couplings is necessary to test the validity of the SM and the presence of new physics up to a high energy scale. Since the tree-level couplings of the $WW\gamma$ and WWZ vertices are fixed by the SM, any deviations from their SM values would indicate the new physics beyond the SM. The photoproduction of the W and Z bosons through triple gauge boson interactions in the lepton-hadron colliders HERA+LC and in the Large Hadron electron Collider (LHeC) has been studied theoretically in the papers [1]-[3] and [4], respectively. An investigation of the potential of the LHeC to probe anomalous $WW\gamma$ coupling has been presented in [5], [6].

The present bounds on the anomalous $WW\gamma$ and WWZ couplings are provided by the LEP [7], Tevatron [8], [9] and LHC [10], [11] experiments.

Recently, the ATLAS [10], [11] and CMS [12], [13] Collaborations have established updated constraints on the anomalous $WW\gamma$ and WWZ couplings from the $\gamma W(Z)$ and W^+W^- production processes. The results from ATLAS and

CMS experiments based on two-parameter analysis of the anomalous couplings are given in Table I.

In this work, we investigate the $ep\rightarrow\nu_e q\gamma X$ and $ep\rightarrow\nu_e qZX$ processes with anomalous $WW\gamma$ and WWZ couplings at the high energy electron-proton collider LHeC and FCC-ep (Future Circular Collider-electron proton) collider [14]. LHeC is considered to be realised by accelerating electrons 140 GeV and colliding them with the 7 TeV protons. We take into account the energies of the FCC-ep as 80 GeV for electron beam and 50 TeV for proton beam. We also consider the possibility of the electron beam polarization at LHeC [15] and FCC-ep which extends the sensitivity to anomalous triple gauge boson couplings.

TABLE I
THE AVAILABLE 95% C.L. TWO-PARAMETER BOUNDS ON ANOMALOUS COUPLINGS $(\Delta\kappa_\gamma, \lambda_\gamma)$ AND $(\Delta\kappa_Z, \lambda_Z)$ FROM THE ATLAS AND CMS EXPERIMENTS

	ATLAS	CMS	ATLAS (upper-lower)	CMS (upper-lower)
$\Delta\kappa_\gamma$	-0.420,0.480	-0.250, 0.250	0.900	0.500
λ_γ	-0.068,0.062	-0.050, 0.042	0.130	0.092
$\Delta\kappa_Z$	-0.045,0.045	-0.160, 0.180	0.090	0.340
λ_Z	-0.063,0.063	-0.055, 0.055	0.126	0.110

II. ANOMALOUS COUPLINGS

The $WW\gamma$ and WWZ interaction vertices are described by an effective Lagrangian with the coupling constants $g_{WW\gamma}$ and g_{WWZ} and dimensionless parameter pairs $(\Delta\kappa_\gamma, \lambda_\gamma)$ and $(\Delta\kappa_Z, \lambda_Z)$

$$L = ig_{WW\gamma} [g_1^\gamma (W_{\mu\nu}^\dagger W^\mu A^\nu - W^{\mu\nu} W_\mu^\dagger A_\nu) + \kappa_\gamma W_\mu^\dagger W_\nu A^{\mu\nu} + \frac{\lambda_\gamma}{m_W^2} W_{\rho\mu}^\dagger W_\nu^\mu A^{\nu\rho}] + ig_{WWZ} [g_1^Z (W_{\mu\nu}^\dagger W^\mu Z^\nu - W^{\mu\nu} W_\mu^\dagger Z_\nu) + \kappa_Z W_\mu^\dagger W_\nu Z^{\mu\nu} + \frac{\lambda_Z}{m_W^2} W_{\rho\mu}^\dagger W_\nu^\mu Z^{\nu\rho}] \quad (1)$$

where $g_{WW\gamma} = g_e = g \sin\theta_W$ and $g_{WWZ} = g \cos\theta_W$. In general these vertices involve six C and P conserving couplings [16]. However, the electromagnetic gauge invariance requires that $g_1^\gamma = 1$. The anomalous couplings are defined as $\kappa_\gamma = 1 + \Delta\kappa_\gamma$ where $V=\gamma, Z$ and $g_1^Z = 1 + \Delta g_1^Z$. The $W_{\mu\nu}$, $Z_{\mu\nu}$ and $A_{\mu\nu}$ are the field strength tensors for the W - boson, Z - boson and photon, respectively.

The one-loop corrections to the $WW\gamma$ and WWZ vertices within the framework of the SM have been studied in [17]-[19]. These corrections to the $\Delta\kappa_V$ and λ_V have been found to be of the order of 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} , respectively. The values of the

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couplings $\kappa_V = \kappa_Z = 1$ and $\lambda_V = \lambda_Z = 0$ correspond to the case of the SM. Since unitarity restricts the $WW\gamma$ and WWZ couplings to their SM values at very high energies, the triple gauge couplings are modified as $\Delta\kappa_V(q^2) = \Delta\kappa_V(0)/(1+q^2/\Lambda^2)^2$ and $\lambda_V(q^2) = \lambda_V(0)/(1+q^2/\Lambda^2)^2$ where $V = \gamma, Z$. The q^2 is the square of momentum transfer into the process and Λ is the new physics energy scale. The $\Delta\kappa_V(0)$ and $\lambda_V(0)$ are the values of the anomalous couplings at $q^2 = 0$. We assume the values of the anomalous couplings remain approximate constant in the interested energy scale ($\Lambda^2 > q^2$). We take $\Delta\kappa_V$ and λ_V as free parameters in the considered range and find the bounds on these couplings effectively. For the numerical calculations, we have implemented interactions terms in the CalcHEP [20].

Fig. 1 Representative Feynman diagrams for subprocess $eq \rightarrow \nu_e \gamma q'$

Fig. 2 Representative Feynman diagrams for subprocess $eq \rightarrow \nu_e Z q'$

III. PRODUCTION CROSS SECTIONS FOR LHEC

According to the effective Lagrangian, the anomalous vertices for triple gauge interactions $WW\gamma$ and WWZ are presented in the Feynman graphs as shown in Figs. 1 and 2. In order to calculate the cross sections for the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q\gamma X$ and $ep \rightarrow \nu_e qZX$, we apply the transverse momentum cut on photon and jet as $p_T^\gamma > 50$ GeV, $p_T^j > 20$ GeV; missing transverse momentum cut $p_T^{\cancel{e}} > 20$ GeV, pseudorapidity cuts $|\eta_{\gamma,j}| < 3.5$; a cone radius cut between photons and jets $\Delta R_{\gamma,j} > 1.5$. Using these cuts and the parton distribution functions of CTEQ6L [21], the total cross sections of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q\gamma X$ as a function of anomalous couplings $\Delta\kappa_\gamma$ and λ_γ for $E_e = 140$ GeV with electron beam polarizations $P_e = \pm 0.8$ and $P_e = 0$ are

presented in Figs. 3 and 4. In Figs. 5 and 6, the total cross sections of the $ep \rightarrow \nu_e qZX$ process are given for the same energy. It is clear from these figures that the polarization ($P_e = -0.8$) enhances the cross sections according to the unpolarized case.

Fig. 3 The cross section depending on anomalous coupling $\Delta\kappa_\gamma$ of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q\gamma X$ at $E_e = 140$ GeV for different electron beam polarizations

Fig. 4 The cross section depending on anomalous coupling λ_γ of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q\gamma X$ at $E_e = 140$ GeV for different electron beam polarizations

Fig. 5 The cross section depending on anomalous $\Delta\kappa_Z$ coupling of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e qZX$ for $E_e = 140$ GeV

Fig. 6 The cross section depending on anomalous λ_Z coupling of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q ZX$ for $E_e = 140$ GeV

IV. ANALYSIS FOR LHEC

In order to estimate the sensitivity to the anomalous $WW\gamma$ and WWZ couplings, we use the χ^2 function:

$$\chi^2(\Delta\kappa_V, \lambda_V) = \left(\frac{\sigma_{SM} - \sigma(\Delta\kappa_V, \lambda_V)}{\Delta\sigma_{SM}} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\sigma_{SM} = \sigma_{SM} \sqrt{\delta_{stat.}^2}$ with $\delta_{stat.} = 1/\sqrt{N_{SM}}$ and $N_{SM} = \sigma_{SM} L$. In our calculations, we consider that two of the couplings $(\Delta\kappa, \lambda)$ are assumed to deviate from their SM value. We estimate the sensitivity to the anomalous couplings at 95 C.L. at the LHeC for the integrated luminosities of 10 fb^{-1} and 100 fb^{-1} . The contour plots of anomalous couplings in $\Delta\kappa_\gamma - \lambda_\gamma$ plane for the integrated luminosities of 10 fb^{-1} and 100 fb^{-1} at electron beam energies $E_e = 140$ GeV are given in Fig. 7. The contour plots of anomalous couplings in $\Delta\kappa_Z - \lambda_Z$ plane for the integrated luminosities of 10 fb^{-1} and 100 fb^{-1} at electron beam energies of $E_e = 140$ GeV are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7 Two dimensional 95% C.L. contour plot anomalous couplings in the $\lambda_\gamma - \Delta\kappa_\gamma$ plane for the integrated luminosity of 10 fb^{-1} and 100 fb^{-1} at electron beam energy $E_e = 140$ GeV with polarization $P_e = -0.8$

Fig. 8 Two-dimensional 95% C.L. contour plot of anomalous couplings in the $\lambda_Z - \Delta\kappa_Z$ plane for the integrated luminosity of 10 fb^{-1} and 100 fb^{-1} at electron beam energy $E_e = 140$ GeV with polarization $P_e = -0.8$

The difference of the upper and lower bounds on the anomalous couplings $\Delta\kappa_V$ and λ_V (where $V = \gamma, Z$) can be written as

$$\delta\Delta\kappa_V = \Delta\kappa_V^{upper} - \Delta\kappa_V^{lower}, \delta\lambda_V = \lambda_V^{upper} - \lambda_V^{lower} \quad (3)$$

The current limits on anomalous couplings and the difference of the upper and lower bounds for electron beam energies of 140 GeV with integrated luminosities $L_{int} = 10 \text{ fb}^{-1}$ and 100 fb^{-1} at LHeC with the unpolarized (polarized) electron beam are given in Table II. We have obtained two-parameter limits on $\delta\Delta\kappa_\gamma$ and $\delta\lambda_\gamma$ which can be compared to the ATLAS and CMS results. However, the limits on $\delta\lambda_Z$ is found to be much more sensitive than the current limits.

TABLE II
 THE 95% C.L. CURRENT LIMITS ON THE ANOMALOUS COUPLINGS AND THE DIFFERENCE OF THE UPPER AND LOWER BOUNDS FOR ELECTRON BEAM ENERGY OF $E_e = 140$ GeV WITH $L_{int} = 100 \text{ fb}^{-1}$ FOR POLARIZED AND UNPOLARIZED ELECTRON BEAM

Pe	$\Delta\kappa_\gamma$	$\delta\Delta\kappa_\gamma$	λ_γ	$\delta\lambda_\gamma$
-0.8	-0.182, 0.793	0.975	-0.039, 0.079	0.118
0	0.192, 0.798	0.990	-0.041, 0.081	0.122
0.8	0.251, 0.844	1.095	-0.047, 0.086	0.133
Pe	$\Delta\kappa_Z$	$\delta\Delta\kappa_Z$	λ_Z	$\delta\lambda_Z$
-0.8	-0.143, 0.142	0.285	-0.001, 0.008	0.009
0	0.273, 0.089	0.362	-0.003, 0.009	0.012
0.8	0.253, 0.215	0.468	-0.004, 0.010	0.014

V. PRODUCTION CROSS SECTIONS FOR FCC-EP

For calculate the cross sections for the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q \gamma X$ and $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q ZX$, we apply the transverse momentum cut on photon and jet as $p_T^Y > 20$ GeV, $p_T^j > 20$ GeV; missing transverse momentum cut $p_T^{\nu} > 20$ GeV, pseudorapidity cuts $\eta_{\nu, j}$ the range of between -5 and 0; Using these cuts and the parton distribution functions of CTEQ6M [14], the total cross sections of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q \gamma X$ as a function of anomalous couplings $\Delta\kappa_\gamma$ and λ_γ for $E_e = 80$ GeV with ($P_e = \pm 0.8$) and

without ($P_e=0$) electron beam polarization are presented in Figs. 9 and 10. It is clear from these figures that the polarization ($P_e=-0.8$) enhances the cross sections according to the unpolarized case.

Fig. 9 The cross section depending on anomalous coupling $\Delta\kappa_\gamma$ of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q \gamma X$ at $E_e=80$ GeV for different electron beam polarizations

Fig. 10 The cross section depending on anomalous λ_γ coupling of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q \gamma X$ for $E_e=80$ GeV

Fig. 11 The cross section depending on anomalous $\Delta\kappa_Z$ coupling of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q ZX$ for $E_e=80$ GeV

The cross sections depending on anomalous couplings $\Delta\kappa_Z$ and λ_Z of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q ZX$ for $E_e=80$ GeV with $P_e=\pm 0.8$

and without ($P_e=0$) electron beam polarization are presented in Figs. 11 and 12.

Fig. 12 The cross section depending on anomalous λ_Z coupling of the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q ZX$ for $E_e=80$ GeV

VI. ANALYSIS FOR FCC-EP

The contour plots of anomalous couplings in $\Delta\kappa_\gamma - \lambda_\gamma$ plane for the integrated luminosities of 10 fb^{-1} and 100 fb^{-1} at electron beam energies $E_e=80$ GeV are given in Fig. 13. For the process $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q ZX$, we make analysis of the signal and backgrounds when Z decays leptonically, $Z \rightarrow l^+ l^-$ where $l=e, \mu$. The contour plots of anomalous couplings in $\Delta\kappa_Z - \lambda_Z$ plane for the integrated luminosities of 10 fb^{-1} and 100 fb^{-1} at electron beam energies of $E_e=80$ GeV are presented in Fig. 14.

The difference of the upper and lower bounds on the anomalous couplings $\Delta\kappa_V$ and λ_V (where $V=\gamma, Z$) can be written as

$$\delta\Delta\kappa_V = \Delta\kappa_V^{upper} - \Delta\kappa_V^{lower}, \delta\lambda_V = \lambda_V^{upper} - \lambda_V^{lower} \quad (4)$$

The current limits on anomalous couplings and the difference of the upper and lower bounds for electron beam energies of $E_e=80$ GeV with integrated luminosities 100 fb^{-1} at FCC-ep with the unpolarized (polarized) electron beam are given in Table III. We have obtained two-parameter limits on $\delta\Delta\kappa_\gamma$ and $\delta\lambda_\gamma$ which can be compared to the ATLAS and CMS results. However, the current limits on $\delta\lambda_Z$ is found to be much more sensitive at the FCC-ep.

TABLE III
THE 95% C.L. CURRENT LIMITS ON THE ANOMALOUS COUPLINGS AND THE DIFFERENCE OF THE UPPER AND LOWER BOUNDS FOR ELECTRON BEAM ENERGY OF $E_e=80$ GeV WITH $L_{INT}=100 \text{ FB}^{-1}$ FOR POLARIZED ELECTRON BEAM

P_e	$\Delta\kappa_\gamma$	$\delta\Delta\kappa_\gamma$	λ_γ	$\delta\lambda_\gamma$
-0.8	-0.100:1.001	1.101	-0.026:0.039	0.0650
P_e	$\Delta\kappa_Z$	$\delta\Delta\kappa_Z$	λ_Z	$\delta\lambda_Z$
-0.8	-0.019:0.301	0.320	-0.0011:0.0012	0.0023

Fig. 13 Two dimensional 95% C.L contour plot anomalous couplings in the $\lambda_\gamma - \Delta\kappa_\gamma$ plane for the integrated luminosity of 10 fb^{-1} and 100 fb^{-1} at electron beam energy $E_e = 80 \text{ GeV}$ with polarization $P_e = -0.8$

Fig. 14 Two-dimensional 95% C.L contour plot of anomalous couplings in the $\lambda_Z - \Delta\kappa_Z$ plane for the integrated luminosity of 10 fb^{-1} and 100 fb^{-1} at electron beam energy $E_e = 80 \text{ GeV}$ with polarization

VII. CONCLUSION

The $WW\gamma$ and WWZ anomalous interactions through the processes $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q \gamma X$ and $ep \rightarrow \nu_e q Z X$ can be studied independently at the LHeC and FCC-ep. We obtain two-parameter accessible ranges of triple gauge boson anomalous couplings at LHeC and FCC-ep with the polarized electron beam at the energies $E_e = 140 \text{ GeV}$ and $E_p = 7 \text{ TeV}$, and $E_e = 80 \text{ GeV}$ and $E_p = 50 \text{ TeV}$, respectively. Our limits compare with the results from two-parameter analysis given by ATLAS and CMS Collaborations [10]-[13]. We find that the sensitivities to anomalous couplings $\Delta\kappa_V$ ($V = \gamma, Z$) will be of the order of 10^{-1} , which is an order of magnitude larger than the SM loop level sensitivity of 10^{-2} , however a measurement of these couplings above 10^{-2} would offer a possible new physics signal. We conclude that the anomalous couplings λ_γ and λ_Z can be well constrained with the sensitivity of the order of 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} at the FCC-ep with polarized electron beam. The LHeC and FCC-ep could give complementary information about anomalous couplings compared to Tevatron and LHC.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work of O.C. is partially supported by State Planning Organisation (DPT) - Ministry of Development under the grant No. DPT2006K-120470. A.S. would like to thank Abant Izzet Baysal University Department of Physics where of part this study was carried out for their hospitality

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